

register

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	name	varchar(30)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
2	pwd	varchar(150)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
3	cpwd	varchar(150)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
4	email <input type="checkbox"/>	varchar(50)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
5	mobile	bigint(20)			No	None		
6	address1	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
7	address2	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
8	address3	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
9	lat1	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
10	lon1	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
11	lat2	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
12	lon2	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
13	lat3	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
14	lon3	varchar(25)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
15	token	varchar(6)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None		
16	flag	int(11)			No	None		

Indexes

Keyname	Type	Unique	Packed	Column	Cardinality	Collation	Null	Comment
PRIMARY	BTREE	Yes	No	email		A	No	
				mobile	6	A	No	
email	BTREE	Yes	No	email	6	A	No	

Partitions

No partitioning defined!

Information

Space usage

Data	3.1	KiB
Index	3.0	KiB
Overhead	0	B
Effective	6.1	KiB
Total	6.1	KiB

Row statistics

Format	dynamic
Collation	latin1_swedish_ci
Rows	6
Row length	524 B
Row size	1,036 B
Next autoindex	1
Creation	Nov 14, 2021 at 09:08 AM
Last update	Nov 14, 2021 at 09:08 AM
Last check	Nov 14, 2021 at 09:08 AM